

Determination of bismuth in presence of diverse ions: The procedure for the determination of bismuth in the presence of diverse ions is the same as described above except that the pH of the solution was adjusted after the addition of a diverse ion. Alkali metals, alkaline earths, ammonium, Zn(II), Mn(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Zr(IV) and tungstate do not interfere with the determination and Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(II), Fe(III), Pb(II) and Cd(II) can be masked with EDTA. Ag(I), Hg(II), Cu(II) and Sb(III) interfere with the determination. The results are recorded in Table 1. The tolerance of the diverse ions has been studied only upto the amounts mentioned in the table.

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Studies on Lanthanide DAMO-SAO Mixed Complexes

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SEVERAL Lanthanide simple oximates¹⁻⁵ and mixed complexes where oximes are used as primary ligands and 1,10-phenanthroline, oxine and pyridine-2, aldoxime as the second ligand were prepared and characterised⁶. This communication details the preparation and characterisation of certain Lanthanide mixed complexes using DAMO as primary ligand and SAO as second ligand.

The simple Lanthanide diacetylmonoximate were prepared by the method reported by Rao *et al.*⁵. Mixed complexes were prepared adopting the following procedure.

A weighed quantity of Lanthanide diacetylmonoximate was dissolved in ethanol and mixed with a calculated amount (Mole Ratio 1 : 3) of Salicylal-doxime. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.8 by addition of alcoholic ammonia. The resulting solution was evaporated on a steam bath when the solid separated. The excess ligand was washed with ether. All the compounds were vacuum dried over fused calcium chloride for 48 hrs. Analytical data of the mixed complexes is detailed in Table 1. The conductivity data of the compounds indicated that they are all non electrolytes.

Results and Discussion

The ligand DAMO has a band in u.v. region around 220 nm (log $\epsilon = 4.04$) and SAO has two bands at 260 nm (log $\epsilon = 4.22$) and 305 nm (log $\epsilon = 3.78$). Both the ligand bands have been located in the mixed complexes with a change in log ϵ values as compared with free ligand values. The change gives an indication of the existence of both the ligands in the complexes and of their strong interaction with lanthanide ions.

In the visible region the characteristic band of Pr³⁺ and Sm³⁺ ions could not be located in this investigation. Only the 576 nm band of Nd³⁺ ion is located, with a red shift, around 580-585 nm (log $\epsilon = 1.49$). This red shift can, as a first approximation be correlated with (i) dsp hybridisation, (ii) possible involvement of 4f electrons in chelation, and (iii) strong interaction of Nd³⁺ ion with the ligands.

In the i.r. region the ligand DAMO exhibits two bands around 3410 cm⁻¹ and 3350 cm⁻¹ due to OH stretch of the oxime. SAO exhibits only one band at 3350 cm⁻¹ and is assigned to the presence of the oxime group with probably intramolecular hydrogen bonding. In the lanthanide salicylal-doximates reported⁵ the 3350 cm⁻¹ band has suffered a negative shift in some cases while it disappeared in the rest.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF LANTHANIDE COMPLEXES

Complex	% Metal		% Chloride		% Nitrogen	
	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.
Y(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	22.39	22.29	17.88	17.50	6.97	6.80
La(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	31.08	30.09	15.88	15.00	6.26	6.02
Pr(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	31.37	31.20	15.82	15.60	6.23	6.20
Nd(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	31.87	31.27	15.70	15.50	6.189	5.99
Sm(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	32.78	32.50	15.48	15.40	6.105	6.08
Gd(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	33.77	33.34	15.25	15.00	6.015	6.00
Dy(DAMO) ₁ (SAO) ₁ Cl ₂	34.52	33.90	15.09	14.95	5.95	5.80

In this investigation there is a general lowering of the OH stretch contributed by both the ligands in the 3350 cm^{-1} region. The change in intensity and lowering can be taken as an indication of N-M bond formation and also elimination of the phenolic proton of SAO during complexation.

DAMO exhibits a band around 1655 cm^{-1} due to C = O stretch. This band has disappeared in all the complexes indicating the involvement of carbonyl group in bond formation. The ligand SAO has two bands at 1620 and 1570 cm^{-1} which are due to C = N stretch. The one at 1620 cm^{-1} is slightly shifted to a higher frequency where as the 1570 cm^{-1} band could not be located in the mixed complexes. The band at 1500 cm^{-1} in SAO due to orthosubstituted benzene ring is shifted to a lower frequency and located at 1480 cm^{-1} in all the mixed complexes. The band around 975 cm^{-1} arising out of the N-O stretch of the oxime is located with slight shift in all the mixed complexes.

From an examination of the above data it can be concluded that both the ligands DAMO and SAO are involved in complexation. The oxime protons are intact whereas the proton of the phenolic OH of SAO is eliminated during complexation. General structure assigned to the several lanthanide mixed complexes is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

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Solid State Studies on Polymerization and Depolymerization of Heteropoly Tungstate ion with Fe^{+2} as the Hetero Atom

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A new condensation inorganic polymer, $\text{Na}_6[\text{FeW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$, has been prepared and characterised on the basis of analytical and molecular weight determinations. The thermal depolymerization of the product has been studied extensively.

Of condensation of inorganic polymers¹, no reports on 12-heteropoly tungstoferrate are found in the literature. The present note is an attempt towards that line.

To 100 ml. of aqueous solution of M/5 sodium tungstate, 30 ml. of ferrous sulphate was gradually added with constant stirring at a controlled temperature of 80° in a thermostat. After half an hour interval, glacial acetic acid was added dropwise to this solution till pH comes just in the range of 3.5 to 3.7. The solution was boiled constantly for 6 hr., evaporated to half of its volume and allowed to crystallise in vacuo when bright needle shaped crystalline compound came out which was washed with ethanol and recrystallised thrice from hot water. Analysis of the compound was carried out by usual chemical methods and sodium was estimated by flame photometric method. (Found: Na, 3.69; Fe, 1.68; W, 62.09; H, 1.69%. Calcd. for $\text{Na}_6[\text{FeW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Na, 3.89; Fe, 1.57; W, 62.22; H, 1.58%). Hydrogen has been analysed by element estimation method.

From the analytical data, the molecular formula of the compound, as per Kegging's view², comes out to be $\text{Na}_6[\text{FeW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]\cdot 28\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Molecular weight Determinations: The cryoscopic method, as has been applied successfully by Alexander³ and by Thilo and Krüger⁴ for molecular weight determinations of polymerised silicic acids, condensed phosphates etc., in water and molten sodium sulphate decahydrate, has also been applied here for the determination of the approximate molecular weight of the compound, in the same condition i.e., in water and in molten sodium sulphate decahydrate^{3,4}. This determination showed the molecular weight of the polymeric compound to be 3495 as compared with the calculated value 3544.11. To know the accurate degree of polymerization this result has been corroborated by X-ray crystal diffraction technique⁵ for molecular weight determinations of heteropoly acids. The crystal diffraction data of the compound are $a = 11.32$, $b = 14.40$, $c = 27.12 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, volume per unit cell $V = 4420.776 \text{ \AA}^3$. Number of molecules per unit cell $Z = 2$. Pycnometric measurement gives the